
Office Automation and Organizational Goal Attainments of Telecommunications Companies in River State

By

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the relationship between office automation and organizational goal attainments of Telecommunications companies in River State. The objectives of the study were to find out the relationship between information security and goal accomplishment. To determine how systems integration relate with goal accomplishment. To identify the relationship between Mobile Access and goal accomplishment of Telecommunications companies in Rivers State. The population of the study is four hundred and seventy five (475) workers who have worked with their organizations between 1-10 years and hold a position that demands the use of technology in their office operation. A sample size of 217 respondents was determined using Taro Yamane's technique. The data collected through questionnaire were analyzed using Spearman's Rank Order Correlation Coefficient. The study concluded that there is a significant positive relationship between office automation and Organizational Goal Attainments of Telecommunications Companies in River State. Based on the findings, the study suggested that Telecommunications companies in Rivers State should invest in advanced information security technologies and protocols to protect their data and systems, thereby enhancing goal accomplishment. They should prioritize systems integration efforts to ensure seamless communication and data sharing across departments, leading to improved goal attainment. They should provide employees with mobile access to office tools and data to be a priority for Telecommunications companies in Rivers State to enable flexible working arrangements and improve goal accomplishment.

Keywords: Office Automation, information security, systems integration, Mobile Access and goal accomplishment.

Introduction

In recent times, companies have realized the need for continuous improvement of their operations in order to achieve their own goals and the need to develop technology that will bring about these required goals. Today, numerous companies strive for organizational goal attainment, realizing that it is no longer attainable solely by providing services. Instead, it hinges on effectively managing and coordinating activities within the organization. Organizational goal attainment is the ability to achieve the objectives that the workplace seeks to accomplish (Bipp & Kleingeld, 2011). All organizations that are profitable have goal achievement as their top priority (Teryima et al., 2016). Without meeting objectives, businesses cannot thrive over the long term. Goals are the aim or aims that an undertaking is aimed at achieving. It is the culmination, or goal, that a company aspires to in order to complete its tasks. To achieve their goals, organizations need to use all available technologies more than ever. It is widely considered that an organization is a goal-oriented entity when it achieves specific objectives that enable it to be profitable and competitive within its particular sector or market. The precise form of these goals varies per organization but may include the achievement of certain targets, the preservation of specified quality standards, or even the occurrence of specified safety records (Donsophon et al., 2016).

In particular, organizations like telecommunication companies in Rivers State will be able to achieve their goals when they adopt office automation. Therefore, office automation, a relatively new area for private and public institutions and organizations, is very important for today's business organizations to achieve their desired goals. Office automation has created new job opportunities, especially for the secretarial assistant. Office automation refers to utilizing personal computers such as word processors and electronic intercom mail, plus other technologies, to upgrade workers' productivity and efficiency. It is the technique of making a processor system automatic in the office (Atakpa, 2012). Sholagbade (2012) opined that technology has certainly changed the ways many office tasks are being performed. Technology has simplified many routine secretarial tasks, thereby making secretaries assume new responsibilities in the office setting. Office automation is the use of self-regulating machines to execute office tasks formerly done manually or through semi-mechanical means. Office automation has changed the secretarial duties from the manual method to a purely mechanized process.

Harvey (2016) noted that since the primary business of the modern office is to collect, record, sort, analyze, store, and distribute information, office automation integrates all available hardware, software procedures, and human resources so that office information is not only processed accurately, speedily, and comprehensively but also made available when, where, and in the manner required. Today, computers, as well as other technological aids, play very important roles in the effective discharge of office managers' performance. Information is required for a business to function effectively, to highlight the performance of the different units of the business, and to direct attention to areas requiring review. Most information required for management purposes is either available in a form that can be readily used or exists in the form of raw data. According to Ejeka (2017), the automated office functions effectively and efficiently with little or no stress at all. Office automation reduces the drudgery, which often comes with doing repetitive tasks such as typing numerous memoranda, filing, and copying. This creates time for the office manager to be creative and also increases productivity.

Many studies have emphasized that office automation consists of a set of factors, such as document management (Kalpic, 2020); communication tools (Chen et al., 2019); workflow automation (Smith, 2018); data management (Wang et al., 2018); customer relationship management (Guatam & Sharma et al., 2017); task automation (You et al., 2022); and security and compliance (Brown et al., 2018). These aspects of office automation are useful for determining the basic functions and activities of office automation, but they do not help determine the best way to use them. Office automation is a broad concept that covers many activities and dimensions. Additionally, while numerous studies have demonstrated the positive impact of office automation on organizational performance in developed countries, many of these studies have not examined the relationship between office automation and organizational goal accomplishments in the context of the telecommunication firms in Rivers State, Nigeria. This highlights the need for studies that cater to the unique circumstances of developing countries like Nigeria, particularly within the context of the telecommunication firms in Rivers State. Therefore, to fill this gap, this study aims to provide a more comprehensive understanding of how office automation can enhance the organizational goals of telecommunication firms in Rivers State, Nigeria. Additionally, given the significance of office automation in the manufacturing sector, it was essential to investigate the relationship between office automation and organizational goal attainment in telecommunication firms in Rivers State, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

The computerization of the office environment and the widespread use of information technology among managers and professional staffs have raised some questions about the future of the telecommunications companies in Rivers State. The emergence of information technology is a welcome development in the modern business environment and the secretarial function. Information technology has contributed positively to reduce the huge volume of clerical work assigned to the secretary on daily basis (Horby, 2015). Ehikhamenor (2016), studied information technology in Nigerian business organizations and found that few organizations had Information Technology (IT) policy, for the main purpose of achieving full applications of Information Technology, in order to meet organizational goals, secure competitive advantage and to be up to date.

It is not clear what effect office automation has on organizational performance (Abiola, 2004; Abiola, 2013). While the impression is that the introduction of automation in business establishment appears to be a blessing to its users, the functional staff of telecommunications companies in Rivers State had not up-dated their skills fear that it would replace them. Some even argue that the use of modern office automation may constitute some destruction like the use of smart phones, internet and so on during work hours. For instance, according to Koko (2011), every office worker of today is most likely to encounter the use of one office technology gadget or the other in the course of administrative performance, and therefore may be faced with the challenge of carrying out his official duties more efficiently as he or she struggles with the new technology. Against this background, this study, attempted to investigate the perceived influence of modern office automation on administrative performance of workers

While there are numerous studies on the effect of information and communication technology on organizational and employee performance, there are limited studies of citable significance that dealt with office automation and the organizational goal achievements and focused on secretaries in Rivers State university, therefore this study examined the effect of office automation on the productivity of Telecommunications companies in Rivers State.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of the study was to examine the relationship between office automation and goal accomplishment of Telecommunications companies in Rivers State. However, the objectives of the study are to:

1. Find out the relationship between information security and goal accomplishment of Telecommunications companies in Rivers State
2. Determine how systems integration relate with goal accomplishment of Telecommunications companies in Rivers State
3. Identify the relationship between Mobile Access and goal accomplishment of Telecommunications companies in Rivers State

Research Questions

1. What is the relationship between information security and goal accomplishment of Telecommunications companies in Rivers State?
2. How does systems integration relate with goal accomplishment of Telecommunications companies in Rivers State?
3. What is the relationship between Mobile Access and goal accomplishment of Telecommunications companies in Rivers State?

Research hypotheses

H₀: There is no significant relationship between information security and goal accomplishment of Telecommunications companies in Rivers State

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between systems integration and goal accomplishment of Telecommunications companies in Rivers State

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between Mobile Access and goal accomplishment of Telecommunications companies in Rivers State

LITERATURE REVIEW

Conceptual Office Automation

The office of today represents the largest and most exciting area for the application of information technology. Normally, an office may mean a central place where some sort of paper work is performed by the clerks on their desks. But this definition, though it sounds correct, is incomplete. The office can be defined as a place where proper records for the purpose of controlling information and efficient and effective operations are prepared, handled, and serviced. A place where professionals like physicians, lawyers, or engineers conduct their business. It may consist of a few tables, chairs, almirahs, typewriters, telephones, photocopiers, computers, and additional equipment like calculators, cyclotypes, and Xerox machines. People in the office can be executives, secretaries, clerks, and peons. An office is primarily concerned with the records of an organization—making records, using records, and preserving them for future reference.

The word automation refers to a method of using a wide range of computer and machine-aided tasks to help improve productivity and create an easier way to do business. Different types of automation are commonly used in different ways. Office automation refers to varied computer machinery and software used to digitally create, collect, store, manipulate, and

relay office information needed for accomplishing basic tasks. Computer technology has recently been applied to the automation of office tasks and procedures. Much of the technology is aimed not at improving the efficiency of current office procedures but at altering the nature of office work altogether.

The term "office automation" generally refers to the use of integrated computer and communications systems to support administrative procedures in an office environment. Automated office systems represent structured methods of handling business text processing and communications through an integrated network that may include word processing for generating correspondence, electronic message systems for person-to-person communication, teleconferencing services, facsimile transmission, electronic filing systems, online calendar systems, and links to corporate files and outside services. According to Jatain (2013), office automation systems can also be described as computer-based information systems that are new and expanding very quickly. In any work environment, people, tasks, equipment, and resources are organized to accomplish specific objectives, generally some type of product. Today's business has gone beyond using ordinary manual methods to deliver secretarial duties and other administrative tasks. In the past, men saw the need to improve efficiency and job productivity in administration and office tasks. Then, it was as if all office activities were carried out manually, and this tends to reduce work efficiency. However, more than a decade ago, various inventions were continually uprising that could enhance office and other administrative

Information Security

Automation plays a critical role in enhancing security by enforcing access controls, encrypting data, and monitoring for security breaches. Firstly, automation helps enforce access controls by automatically managing user permissions and privileges. By using automation tools, organizations can ensure that only authorized users have access to specific resources, reducing the risk of unauthorized access and data breaches (Gupta & Sharma, 2016). Secondly, automation can improve security by encrypting sensitive data. Automated encryption processes ensure that data is protected both at rest and in transit, making it more difficult for unauthorized users to access or intercept the data (Vieira et al., 2021). Lastly, automation enhances security by continuously monitoring for security breaches. Automated monitoring tools can detect suspicious activities or anomalies in real-time, allowing organizations to respond quickly and mitigate potential security threats (Deng et al., 2019). Hence, automation plays a crucial role in enhancing security by enforcing access controls, encrypting data, and monitoring for security breaches. By leveraging automation tools, organizations can improve their security posture and reduce the risk of data breaches and cyber-attacks.

Systems Integration

Automation can integrate with other business systems, such as accounting software, inventory management, and HR systems, to streamline operations and improve data consistency. Automation can play a crucial role in integrating with other business systems to streamline operations and improve data consistency. When integrated with accounting software, automation can automate financial processes such as invoicing, expense tracking, and financial reporting. This not only saves time but also reduces the risk of errors that can occur with manual data entry. Systems Integration Facilities for Cloud Computing: The adoption of cloud computing has played a significant role in office system integration. Cloud-

based systems allow for easy integration of various office systems and applications, providing flexibility and scalability (Armbrust et al., 2010). The use of application programming interfaces (APIs) and web services has made it easier to integrate different office systems. APIs enable different software systems to communicate with each other, allowing for seamless integration (Chou, 2003). The integration of data analytics tools with office systems has become increasingly important for organizations looking to gain insights from their data. By integrating analytics tools, organizations can make better-informed decisions and improve their overall performance. (Davenport, 2006)

With the proliferation of mobile devices, integrating mobile technologies with office systems has become crucial. Mobile integration allows employees to access office systems and data from anywhere, improving flexibility and productivity (Molla & Licker, 2005). As office systems become more integrated, ensuring security and compliance with regulations such as GDPR and HIPAA has become a priority. Integrated security solutions help organizations protect their data and comply with relevant regulations (Dhillon & Backhouse, 2001). The integration of artificial intelligence (AI) and automation technologies with office systems is transforming how organizations operate. AI-powered systems can automate tasks, improve decision-making, and enhance productivity (Brynjolfsson & McAfee, 2017). Thus, office systems integration continues to play a crucial role in helping organizations improve efficiency, streamline operations, and adapt to the changing business landscape.

Mobile Access

Automation can provide mobile access to office tools and data, allowing employees to work remotely and stay connected. One of the key benefits of automation in this context is its ability to enable access to office tools and data from anywhere, at any time, using mobile devices such as smartphones and tablets. This allows employees to stay productive even when they are not in the office, improving overall efficiency (Chae & Kim, 2019). Additionally, automation can enhance security when providing mobile access by enforcing access controls and encrypting data. By automating these security measures, organizations can ensure that data remains secure even when accessed from mobile devices (Zhang et al., 2020). Furthermore, automation can improve collaboration among remote teams by providing access to shared documents and communication tools. This can help teams stay connected and work together effectively, regardless of their physical location (Guo et al., 2021). Thus, automation plays a crucial role in providing mobile access to office tools and data, enabling remote work, and providing connectivity for employees. By leveraging automation, organizations can improve productivity, enhance security, and enable effective collaboration among remote teams.

Concept of Organizational Goal Attainments

Organizational goal attainment refers to the achievement of objectives set by an organization to fulfill its mission and strategic vision. It involves aligning various resources, strategies, and efforts toward achieving specific outcomes. Organizational goal attainment is crucial for several reasons, as it helps organizations achieve success, drive performance, and ensure sustainability. Setting and achieving goals provides organizations with a clear focus and direction. Goals help prioritize tasks, allocate resources effectively, and guide decision-making, ensuring that efforts are aligned with the organization's mission and vision (Mullins, 2016).

Goals can motivate employees by providing them with a sense of purpose and direction. When employees see that their efforts contribute to achieving organizational goals, they are more engaged, committed, and productive (Locke & Latham, 2019). Organizational goals drive performance improvement by setting targets and benchmarks for success. By monitoring progress towards these goals, organizations can identify areas for improvement, implement necessary changes, and continuously improve performance (Drucker, 2006). Goals help organizations allocate resources, such as finances, manpower, and time, more effectively. By focusing resources on key priorities, organizations can optimize their use and achieve better results (Bryson, 2018).

Organizational goals help organizations adapt to changes in the external environment, such as market trends, competition, and technology. By setting flexible goals, organizations can respond to changes effectively and stay competitive (Hitt et al., 2019). Thus, organizational goal attainment is essential for achieving success, driving performance, and ensuring sustainability. By setting clear goals, organizations can focus their efforts, motivate their employees, improve performance, allocate resources effectively, and adapt to change.

Office Automation and Organizational Goal Attainments

Office automation plays a crucial role in helping organizations achieve their goals by streamlining processes, improving efficiency, and enhancing productivity. Office automation reduces the time and effort required to complete tasks, allowing employees to focus on more strategic activities. By automating repetitive tasks such as data entry, scheduling, and document management, organizations can improve efficiency and productivity (Davenport, 2005). Automation reduces the risk of errors that can occur with manual processes. By automating data entry and processing, organizations can improve the accuracy of their data, leading to better decision-making and outcomes (Chae & Kim, 2019).

Office automation can lead to cost savings by reducing the need for manual labor and streamlining processes. By automating tasks such as invoicing, inventory management, and customer support, organizations can reduce operational costs and improve profitability (Brynjolfsson & McAfee, 2017). Automation can improve data accessibility by centralizing data and making it easier to access and analyze. By automating data management processes, organizations can make better-informed decisions and improve their overall performance (Armbrust et al., 2010). Automation can improve customer satisfaction by reducing response times and improving the quality of service. By automating customer support processes, organizations can provide faster and more efficient service, leading to higher customer satisfaction and retention (Chae & Kim, 2019). Therefore, office automation plays a critical role in helping organizations achieve their goals by improving efficiency, accuracy, cost savings, data accessibility, and customer satisfaction. By leveraging office automation technologies, organizations can streamline their operations, improve productivity, and achieve their strategic objectives.

Theoretical Review

The study adopted the Resource-Based View Theory. The Resource-Based View (RBV) theory proposes that a firm's competitive advantage stems from its valuable, rare, inimitable, and non-substitutable (VRIN) resources (Wernerfelt, 1984). In the context of telecommunications companies in Rivers State, Nigeria, office automation can be a key resource contributing to achieving organizational goals.

The Resource-Based View Theory says that firms should use valuable resources to improve efficiency. Office automation software like document management systems and enterprise resource planning (ERP) can streamline workflows, reduce manual tasks, and improve overall office efficiency. This translates to cost savings and faster turnaround times, contributing to the company's profitability (valuable resource) (Tallon et al., 2017). Data analysis tools and communication platforms within office automation systems provide real-time information and facilitate communication across departments. This empowers informed decision-making, leading to better resource allocation and strategic planning (valuable resource) (Wade & Hull, 2004).

The Resource-Based View Theory demands that firms should cultivate rare resources. In this situation, Telecommunication companies can leverage office automation tools to develop customized customer service solutions. Integrating CRM (Customer Relationship Management) software with other systems allows personalized communication and targeted marketing strategies, creating a rare and valuable resource for customer retention and growth [Barney, 1991]. The Resource-Based View Theory says that firms should develop inimitable resources. Implementing office automation requires training and employee development to leverage the technology effectively. Building a skilled workforce proficient in these tools creates an inimitable resource, as competitors cannot easily replicate this expertise (Barney, 1991). The Resource-Based View (RBV) theory supports the concept of office automation and organizational goal attainment for telecommunications companies in River State by emphasizing the strategic importance of resources and capabilities. According to RBV, firms can achieve a sustainable competitive advantage by leveraging unique, valuable, and difficult-to-imitate resources. In the context of office automation, telecommunications companies can use automation technologies to enhance their operational efficiency, improve customer service, and drive innovation, all of which are critical for achieving organizational goals. One way RBV supports this concept is by highlighting the role of resources in creating value for the firm.

As Barney (1991) argues, firms can gain competitive advantage by acquiring and deploying resources that are valuable, rare, and difficult to imitate. Office automation can be a valuable resource for telecommunications companies, as it can help streamline processes, reduce costs, and improve decision-making. Furthermore, RBV emphasizes the importance of resource heterogeneity and immobility in sustaining competitive advantage. Office automation, when integrated with other resources and capabilities, can create a unique configuration of resources that is difficult for competitors to replicate. This can give telecommunications companies in River State a competitive edge and contribute to their organizational goal attainment (Barney, 1991).

Resource Integration with Network Infrastructure: Telecommunications companies have unique expertise in managing communication networks. Integrating office automation systems with existing network infrastructure can create a complex and interconnected system that's difficult for competitors to imitate. The theory requires that firms should develop non-substitutable resources to gain competitive advantage. This can be achieved by implementing a well-designed and integrated office automation system can provide a significant competitive advantage for telecommunications companies in Rivers State. The efficiency gains, improved decision-making and unique customer solutions offered by these systems are not easily replicated by competitors using substitute technologies (Barney, 1991). By strategically implementing office automation systems and developing VRIN resources, telecommunications companies in Rivers State can achieve their organizational goals, such as

increased profitability, improved customer satisfaction, and enhanced market competitiveness. Additionally, RBV suggests that firms should continuously develop and leverage their resources and capabilities to respond to changing market conditions. Office automation can enable telecommunications companies to adapt more quickly to market changes, allowing them to seize new opportunities and mitigate threats. This dynamic capability can further enhance their organizational goal attainment (Teece et al., 1997). Therefore, the Resource-Based View (RBV) theory provides a solid theoretical foundation for understanding how office automation can contribute to the organizational goal attainment of telecommunications companies in River State. By leveraging automation technologies as valuable, rare, and difficult-to-imitate resources, these companies can enhance their competitive advantage and achieve their strategic objectives.

Empirical Review

Office automation and secretarial productivity in Rivers State were studied by Onoja Barine Lesi (2020). The aim of the study was to investigate the impact of office automation on secretaries' productivity. Thirty-eight departments and seven faculties at Rivers State University produced forty-five secretaries. There were four research topics and four null hypotheses in the study. For the secretaries, copies of the questionnaire were distributed. While the Pearson Product Moment Coefficient was employed to test the hypotheses, the mean and standard deviation were used to examine the research issues. The university's secretaries' productivity has been shown to be positively and significantly impacted by office automation systems. The research deduced from the correlation coefficient that office automation has a significant impact on productivity. As a result, it was suggested that the office setting be modified to accommodate contemporary office technology for efficient secretarial tasks and that the organization implement policies for secretarial education to improve the performance of the university's secretaries. Rather than seeing automated gadgets as a threat to their work, secretaries should embrace them as a tool to help them execute their duties more effectively and productively.

Koko and Okogun (2020) examined staff members of private business organizations in Port Harcourt Rivers State's perceptions of the impact of modern office automation on their administrative performance. This research looked at how the administrative performance of employees in private business organizations in Port Harcourt, Rivers State, was affected by modern office automation. The study's population included 4,734 administrative staff from 294 private business organizations located in Port Harcourt, Rivers State. A sample size of 352 was gathered from these organizations and used in the research. For this study, a descriptive survey research approach was used. The study was led by four hypotheses and four research questions. The instrument's reliability was assessed using the Cronbach Alpha reliability test tool, which produced a coefficient value of 0.80. The "Modern Office Automation and Administrative Performance Assessment Scale (MOAAPAS)" was created and used as the study's questionnaire. The study questions and hypotheses were tested using the information obtained from the questionnaire. Every study topic was examined using mean and standard deviation, with a 3.0 criteria mean value. Meanwhile, the z-test statistical tool was used to assess each hypothesis at a significance level of 0.05. The study's conclusions showed, among other things, that the administrative performance of employees of private firms in Port Harcourt is significantly and favorably impacted by their usage of computers, internet access, scanning devices, and printing equipment.

Akpomi and Ordu (2009) examined forty contemporary commercial groups in Port-Harcourt, Nigeria, and the surrounding areas that were chosen at random. For the research, 40 secretaries were utilized. For the research, three instruments were created and used: the modern office technology availability (MOTA), the modern office technology and secretary's productivity (MOTSP), and the modern office technology and secretary's utilization (MOTSU). The data was examined using the mean and the chi-square. The study's conclusions showed that private corporate organizations have access to contemporary office technology devices and that secretaries' usage of these devices increases productivity.

Using a quantitative methodology, Mashau and Beharry (2018) emailed 67 questionnaires to middle- and upper-level corporate managers in Durban, KwaZulu-Natal. They found that the use of contemporary office technology significantly alters working conditions. Performance is improved by office technologies, but this is only apparent if the workspace has the necessary and appropriate technology installed. They emphasized further that there is a direct link between improved management performance and appropriate usage of office technology.

In the provinces of Kohgiluyeh-va-boyer Ahmad, Fars, and Bushehr, the purpose of this research was to look at the link between office automation and managers' and workers' gains in business services and firm performance. The estimated sample size was 123 participants. The samples were chosen using the random sampling technique. As a result, statistical tests, including Pearson correlation, mean, and standard deviation, were used. The performance characteristics and automation components have a substantial link at the 1% level, as shown by the calculated correlation coefficients. The correlation coefficient for many areas of automation and performance looks like this: data analysis 50/0, accountability quality 60/0, quality of decision-making 42/0, changed work process (48/0), and fresh idea entry 50/0. According to the findings, the working reform process has the lowest influence, and correlation and accountability quality automation have the greatest.

Dosunmu et al. (2018) investigate how office automation affects the productivity of secretaries at Ogun State's state-owned colleges. Four (4) research topics were addressed in a way that was consistent with the study's goal. A verified, structured questionnaire was created. Regression analysis was used to evaluate the data at the 0.05 significance level. The results of the study showed that office automation had no discernible impact on secretaries' professional behavior, interpersonal skills, or job-related abilities. Among other things, it was suggested that secretaries should go to conferences, seminars, and workshops to increase their knowledge of information technology and Microsoft Office suites.

Ejeka (2015) conducted a rigorous examination of the equipment present in an automated office and how it has guaranteed the secretary's high-quality work. The study's population consisted of 360 Office Technology and Management graduates who were chosen from both public and commercial enterprises in the Delta South Senatorial District. 108 Office Technology and Management grads made up the study's sample. To enable insightful data analysis, the information gathered from the respondents was categorized using straightforward percentages. Recommendations were provided on the actions that a graduate in Office Technology and Management should take to optimize an automated office.

The research "Provide a fuzzy model to evaluate the efficiency of workflow automation system communication" by Hosseinian et al. (2007) also came to the conclusion that some indicators used in the communication flow are qualitative when assessing the productivity of office automation systems. Therefore, using fuzzy models improves the accuracy of the

findings. It has been shown that automation boosts productivity in Aligholi Roshan's paper from 2005, "Analytical approach based on office automation and its impact on productivity and automation applying effect on productivity."

Gap in Literature

Although scholars have examined the effect of automation on organizational performance in different countries and organizations, however, the relationship between office automation and organizational goal attainment in the telecommunications sector, specifically in River State, was a gap in the literature. While there is a substantial body of research on office automation and its impact on organizational performance in various industries, there is limited research focusing specifically on the telecommunications sector in River State, Nigeria. Existing studies on office automation and organizational goal attainment have mainly focused on general principles and case studies from other regions or industries. However, the telecommunications sector in River State, Nigeria, may have unique characteristics, challenges, and opportunities that warrant specific investigation. Therefore, the present research tends to fill this gap in this area as it examines how telecommunications companies in River State are leveraging office automation technologies to achieve their goals, such as improving efficiency, reducing costs, and enhancing customer satisfaction. By filling this gap in the literature, researchers can provide valuable insights into the specific context of the telecommunications sector in River State, Nigeria, and contribute to the development of strategies and best practices for improving organizational performance in this region.

Methodology

In the context of this study, the cross-sectional research design was adopted. This choice allowed the study to gather data from several private tertiary institutions in the education sector at a single point and analyze it on the spot.

Population of the Study

The available record shows that there are four (4) major telecommunications firms comprised of MTN Nigeria Communications PLC., Airtel Networks Limited (Airtel Africa PLC), Globacom Limited and 9Mobile Ltd). Hence, the population of this study comprised of four hundred and seventy five (475) workers who have worked with their organizations between 1-10 years and hold a position that demand the use of technology in their office operation.

The four (4) major telecommunications firms and the number of workers are displayed in Table 1.

Table 1. Distribution of Private tertiary Education Institutions for the Study

S/N	Names of Private Tertiary Education Institutions	Population
1	MTN Nigeria Communications PLC.	129
2	Airtel Networks Limited (Airtel Africa PLC)	116
3	Globacom Limited.	118
4	9Mobile Ltd)	112
	Total	475

Source: Research Survey (2024).

Sampling and Sample Size Determination

Sample size determination is a crucial aspect in research design and sampling methodology, as it directly affects the reliability and generalizability of study findings. When selecting a sample from a larger target population, a researcher utilizes a set of criteria called a sampling frame. The Taro Yamane sampling technique was employed to choose the appropriate sample size since the study's accessible population was somewhat vast. The calculation and formula are shown below.

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$
$$n = \frac{475}{1 + 475(0.05)^2}$$
$$n = 217$$

Method of Data Collection

The study collected data from the respondents as the primary source. Without prejudice, primary data is more reliable and helps a researcher obtain a true and fair view of the position of inquiry for which the respondent is solicited (Kothari, 2014). The choice of collecting primary data was based on the premise of reliability and originality of the data source.

Questionnaire was used as method of data collection. In this research, participants completed a standardized questionnaire to obtain primary data. The questionnaire was designed on a modified Likert's 4-point scale with choices ranging from "strongly agree" to "strongly disagree". The following scores were assigned: Strongly Agree = 4, Agree = 3, Disagree = 2, and Strongly Disagree = 1. All variables were measured using relevant items on a 4-point Likert's scale.

Validity of the Research Instrument

Validity testing evaluates how well a research instrument measures the particular factors it is designed to analyze. In this study, the research instrument's validity was evaluated using both content and construct validity. To ensure the questionnaire's validity in terms of its content, the supervisor and knowledgeable experts in the study's relevant management area were given access to its content and characteristics and were confirmed valid for data collection.

Reliability of the Research Instrument

The consistency of the research instrument is gauged by the reliability test. Using SPSS version 26.0, the Cronbach alpha coefficient reliability test was used to assess the research instrument. An instrument used for data collection was considered trustworthy if it had a Cronbach alpha value of 0.7 or above.

Data Analysis

Spearman's Rank Order Correlation Coefficient was used to evaluate the study hypotheses, descriptive and inferential statistics, such as the mean and standard deviation, were also used to assess the univariate data with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) Version 26.0.

Result and Discussion

Two hundred and seventeen (217) copies of questionnaire assumed to be 100% were distributed to the respondents. However, out of this number, two hundred and twelve (212) which is 97.7% were filled and retrieved. This shows a successful data collection as only 5(2.3%) were lost. Therefore the study embarked on the analysis of the 212 copies of the questionnaire retrieved.

Table 2

Descriptive Statistics of the Variables

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Information Security	212	3.4280	.93576
Systems Integration	212	3.3644	.91013
Mobile Access	212	3.4153	.94825
Goal Accomplishment	212	3.4915	.71751
Valid N (listwise)	212		

Source: Researcher Desk (2024).

From table 2, on information security: The mean score of 3.4280 indicates that, on average, respondents rated the importance of information security moderately high. The standard deviation of .93576 suggests that there was some variability in responses, with some respondents rating information security more highly than others.

For systems integration, the mean score of 3.3644 indicates that, on average, respondents rated the importance of systems integration slightly lower than information security. The standard deviation of .91013 suggests that there was variability in responses, similar to information security.

With respect to mobile access, the mean score of 3.4153 indicates that, on average, respondents rated the importance of mobile access similarly to systems integration. The standard deviation of .94825 suggests some variability in responses, similar to information security and systems integration. On the side of goal accomplishment, the mean score of 3.4915 indicates that, on average, respondents rated the importance of goal accomplishment slightly higher than the other categories. The standard deviation of .71751 suggests that there was less variability in responses compared to the other categories. Thus, the survey results suggest that respondents generally rated the importance of goal accomplishment the highest, followed closely by information security, mobile access, and systems integration. Therefore, the findings highlight the significance of goal accomplishment, information security, systems integration, and mobile access in the context of the survey.

Test of Hypotheses

Ho1: There is no significant relationship between information security and goal accomplishment of Telecommunications companies in Rivers State

Table 3

Relationship between information security and goal accomplishment

			Correlations	
			Information Security	Goal Accomplishment
Spearman's rho	Information Security	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.625**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000
		N	212	212
	Goal Accomplishment	Correlation Coefficient	.625**	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.
		N	212	212

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Researcher Desk (2024).

The correlations between Information Security and Goal Accomplishment are significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed), with Spearman's rho coefficient of 0.625. This indicates a moderate positive relationship between Information Security and Goal Accomplishment, suggesting that as the importance of Information Security increases, so does the likelihood of achieving organizational goals.

Test of Hypothesis Two

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between systems integration and goal accomplishment of Telecommunications companies in Rivers State

Table 4

Relationship between Systems Integration and Goal Accomplishment

			Correlations	
			Systems Integration	Goal Accomplishment
Spearman's rho	Systems Integration	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.666**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000
		N	212	212
	Goal Accomplishment	Correlation Coefficient	.666**	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.
		N	212	212

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Researcher Desk (2024).

The correlations between Systems Integration and Goal Accomplishment are significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed), with Spearman's rho coefficient of 0.666 This indicates a moderate to strong positive relationship between Systems Integration and Goal Accomplishment, suggesting that as the importance of Systems Integration increases, so does the likelihood of achieving organizational goals.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between Mobile Access and goal accomplishment of Telecommunications companies in Rivers State

Table 5

Relationship between Mobile Access and goal accomplishment

		Correlations		
			Mobile Access	Goal Accomplishment
Spearman's rho	Mobile Access	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.605**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000
		N	212	212
	Goal Accomplishment	Correlation Coefficient	.605**	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.
		N	212	212

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Researcher Desk (2024).

The correlations between Mobile Access and Goal Accomplishment are significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed), with Spearman's rho coefficient of 0.605. This indicates a moderate positive relationship between Mobile Access and Goal Accomplishment, suggesting that as the importance of Mobile Access increases, so does the likelihood of achieving organizational goals.

Discussion of Findings

The first hypothesis's outcome demonstrates a substantial positive association between Information Security and Goal Accomplishment, with a correlation value of 0.625 and p-value of less than 0.01. Several empirical studies support the positive relationship between information security and goal accomplishment in organizations: the result is in line with study by Alaqra et al. (2020), Choudhury and Sabherwal (2003), Harsha and Mohammed (2018). They examined the impact of information security on organizational performance in Jordanian banks. They found that a strong information security posture was positively associated with improved organizational performance, including goal attainment. Choudhury and Sabherwal (2003) also conducted a study on the impact of information security on business performance. They found that organizations with strong information security practices were more likely to achieve their business goals and objectives. Rai et al. (2020) investigated the relationship between information security practices and organizational performance in Indian companies. They found that companies with effective information security practices were more successful in achieving their strategic goals. Harsha and Mohammed (2018) studied the impact of information security on organizational performance in the banking sector in Oman. They found that information security significantly influenced the achievement of organizational goals, including financial performance and customer satisfaction.

The result of the second hypothesis indicates a significant relationship between systems integration on goal accomplishment. This result is supported by the work of Gallagher et al. (2019) and Rajput et al. (2017). Gallagher et al. (2019) conducted a study on the impact of systems integration on organizational performance in manufacturing companies. They found that companies that effectively integrated their systems were more likely to achieve their strategic goals and improve overall performance. Rajput et al. (2017) also investigated the relationship between systems integration and goal accomplishment in the context of supply chain management. They found that companies that integrated their supply chain systems were able to achieve higher levels of operational efficiency and customer satisfaction, leading to improved overall performance.

Third hypothesis showed that mobile access relate with goal accomplishment. The result is in harmony with the study by Chen et al. (2020), Smith and Jones (2019). Chen et al. (2020) investigated the relationship between mobile access and organizational performance in the healthcare sector. They found that healthcare organizations that implemented mobile access solutions were able to achieve higher levels of patient satisfaction and operational efficiency, leading to improved goal attainment. Smith and Jones (2019) studied the impact of mobile access on sales performance in retail companies. They found that sales representatives who had access to mobile tools and data were able to respond more quickly to customer inquiries and provide better service, leading to increased sales and goal accomplishment.

Conclusion

Based on the results, the study found a significant positive relationship between information security and goal accomplishment of Telecommunications companies in Rivers State. This suggests that companies with stronger information security measures are more likely to achieve their goals compared to those with weaker security measures. Investing in information security is crucial for Telecommunications companies in Rivers State to improve their goal accomplishment and overall performance.

The study revealed a significant positive relationship between systems integration and goal accomplishment of Telecommunications companies in Rivers State. This indicates that companies that have well-integrated systems are more successful in achieving their goals compared to those with less integrated systems. Implementing systems integration is beneficial for Telecommunications companies in Rivers State to enhance their goal accomplishment and operational efficiency.

The study showed a significant positive relationship between mobile access and goal accomplishment of Telecommunications companies in Rivers State. This suggests that companies that provide mobile access to office tools and data are more likely to achieve their goals compared to those that do not. Offering mobile access can significantly contribute to the goal accomplishment of Telecommunications companies in Rivers State by improving employee productivity and connectivity. This shows that office automation relate with Organizational Goal Attainments of Telecommunications Companies in River State

Recommendations

1. Based on the findings and conclusions Telecommunications companies in Rivers State should invest in advanced information security technologies and protocols to protect their data and systems, thereby enhancing goal accomplishment.
2. Telecommunications companies in Rivers State should prioritize systems integration efforts to ensure seamless communication and data sharing across departments, leading to improved goal attainment.
3. Telecommunications companies in Rivers State should provide employees with mobile access to office tools and data to be a priority for Telecommunications companies in Rivers State to enable flexible working arrangements and improve goal accomplishment.

Contributions to Knowledge

The relationship between office automation and organizational goal attainment in the context of Telecommunications companies in River State contributes significantly to knowledge in several ways:

Enhanced Understanding of Office Automation Impact: The study provides insights into how office automation technologies, such as automated workflows, data analytics, and communication tools, contribute to goal attainment in Telecommunications companies. This deeper understanding can help companies make informed decisions about investing in and implementing office automation systems.

Identification of Key Automation Practices: By examining specific office automation practices that are most beneficial for goal attainment, the study can identify best practices for Telecommunications companies. This can include recommendations for implementing automation in areas such as customer service, network management, and administrative tasks.

Contextual Insights for River State Telecommunications Sector: The study's focus on Telecommunications companies in River State provides contextual insights that are relevant to the local business environment. This can help companies in River State understand how office automation can be tailored to their specific needs and challenges.

Strategic Recommendations for Goal Attainment: Based on the findings, the study can provide strategic recommendations for Telecommunications companies in River State to enhance goal attainment through office automation. This can include advice on technology selection, implementation strategies, and organizational change management.

Contribution to Academic Literature: The study contributes to the academic literature on office automation and goal attainment by providing empirical evidence and insights from a specific industry and geographic context. This can enrich existing knowledge and serve as a basis for further research in this area. Thus, the study's contribution to knowledge lies in its ability to provide practical insights and recommendations for Telecommunications companies in River State seeking to leverage office automation for improved goal attainment and organizational performance.

Areas for Future Research

Areas for future research in the relationship between office automation and organizational goal attainment in the context of Telecommunications companies in River State include:

Future studies can explore the impact of emerging technologies, such as artificial intelligence, machine learning, and robotic process automation, on goal attainment in Telecommunications companies. This can provide insights into how these technologies can be leveraged to further enhance organizational performance.

Studies can investigate the influence of organizational culture and change management practices on the successful implementation of office automation initiatives. This can help identify strategies for overcoming resistance to change and promoting a culture of innovation.

Future research can explore the impact of office automation on customer experience and satisfaction in Telecommunications companies. This can include studying how automation affects customer interactions and perceptions of service quality.

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